

Retraction: Helminths Fauna in the Gastrointestinal Tract of Some Domesticated and Non-Domesticated Birds of District Karak, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. Journal of Applied Health Sciences and Medicine 2(1): 15-24, 2022

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The published article [1] has been retracted due to the not following publishing ethics by authors. The authors have published multiple time the same articles in different journals [2] without authorization. Adhering to our complaint's procedure, an investigation was conducted. The decision was made that the article should be retracted. This retraction was approved by the journal editorial members.

References

- [1] K. Ullah, L. Parveen, N. Islam, and M. Ijaz, "Helminths Fauna in the Gastrointestinal Tract of Some Domesticated and Non-Domesticated Birds of District Karak, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan", *J. App. Health Sci. Med.*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 15–24, Mar. 2022.
- [2] Ullah, K., Islam, N., Parveen, L., & Ijaz, M. (2021). Helminths Fauna in the Gastrointestinal Tract of Some Domesticated and Non-Domesticated Birds of District Karak, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. *Journal of Biological Pharmaceutical And Chemical Research*, 8(3), 1-12.